

Annex I: descriptive maps of the videos used in the research “Flipped Learning in the subject «music» of E.S.O. [Compulsory Secondary Education] within a rural environment: impact on students and families”.

Supplementary Material

Maps of the videos that were worked with under a Flipped Learning model during the research in all 4 cases: 1st ESO, 2nd ESO, 3rd ESO and 4th ESO:

<i>1st ESO Descriptions of the videos worked with under the Flipped Learning model during the research</i>									
Objective	Content	BC	Video title	DM	Typology	FDE	ECP	Repository	Questionnaire
Understanding the qualities of sound and its graphic representation	Height in the musical language: the score, the stave, additional lines, treble clef, notes in treble clef, bass clef, notes in bass clef	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Altura i llenguatge musical</i>	02:57	Lesson-Presentation with voice and a music background	edu365.cat Web	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Understanding the meaning of the concept of timbre. Understanding the meaning of	Timbre: voice production	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>La voz humana: generador de sonido</i>	04:36	Lesson-Presentation with text, image of the teacher in some parts,	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot

the concept of voice as a musical instrument					and a music background				
Getting to know the different tessituras of the human voice: high, medium and low-pitched). Acoustically discriminating the different types of voices	Acoustic identification and classification of the different human voice ranges: female and male voices	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Classificació veus femenines</i>	03:20	Lesson-Presentation with text and sound	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
			<i>Classificació veus masculines</i>	03:35	Lesson-Presentation with text and sound	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Getting to know the most representative vocal groups	Visual identification of the different vocal groups	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Les agrupacions vocals</i>	02:37	Infographics animated using the web tool PowToon with text and a music background	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Getting to know the different instrument families and their	Visual and acoustic identification of all the music	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Els instruments de vent fusta</i>	01:29	Lesson-Presentation with text, the teacher's	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot

<p>most representative instruments. Acoustically discriminating between the various types of wood- and metal-wind instruments</p>	<p>instruments and their families</p>		<p><i>Els instruments de vent metall</i></p>	01:01	<p>voice, and sound</p> <p>Lesson-Presentation with text, the teacher's voice, and sound</p>	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	<p>Traditional classroom</p>
			<p><i>Els instruments de percussió</i></p>	01:18	<p>Lesson-Presentation with text, the teacher's voice, and sound</p>	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	
<p>Preparing digital materials for projects and presentations with the use of digital tools following patterns and models</p>	<p>Procedures for content presentation. Preparation of projects and presentations using ICTs for their production and dissemination</p>	<p>5. Transversal elements</p>	<p><i>Núvol de paraules 1ª part</i></p>	03:52	<p>Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background</p>	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	<p>Gamified Kahoot</p>
			<p><i>Núvol de paraules 2ª part</i></p>	03:41	<p>Tutorial with text, the</p>	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	

Autoría: Roig-Vila, Rosabel y Fabra-Brell, Eugenio

					teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background				
--	--	--	--	--	---	--	--	--	--

Note. *BC*: curricular block, *DM*: duration in minutes, *FDE*: elaboration source, *ECP*: enriched with questions

<i>2nd ESO Descriptions of the videos worked with under the Flipped Learning model during the research</i>									
Objective	Content	BC	Video title	DM	Typology	FDE	ECP	Repository	
Elements of music: rhythm, harmony, melody, and timbre	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Elements de la música</i>	05:48	Lesson-Presentation with voice and sound	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom	
Rhythm and beat. Tempo markers. Metronome. Time	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>El ritme y la pulsació</i>	04:49	Infographics animated using the web tool PowToon with text and a music background	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom	
Characteristic instruments of Classicism: keyboard and notes. Height in the musical language: Anglo-Saxon alphabetical notation	1. Listening 3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>Teclat i Notes</i> <i>la part</i> <i>2a part A</i>	05:26 03:36	Lesson-Presentation with text, voice, and image of the teacher in some parts	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	<i>Gamified Kahoot</i>	

		<i>2ª part B</i>	04:43	Lesson- Presentation with text, the teacher's voice, and a music background Lesson- Presentation with text, voice, and image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background					Gamified Kahoot
Intervals	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Els intervals</i>	06:43	Lesson- Presentation with text, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle		Gamified Kahoot
Scales: scale degrees, major scale, minor scale	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Les escales musicals</i>	05:20	Lesson- Presentation with text, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle		Gamified Kahoot
Chords	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Els acords</i>	05:24	Lesson- Presentation with text, voice and image of the	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle		Gamified Kahoot

				teacher in some parts, and a music background				
Procedures for content presentation. Preparation of projects and presentations using ICTs for their production and dissemination	5. Transversal elements	<i>Núvol de paraules 1ª part</i>	03:52	Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
		<i>Núvol de paraules 2ª part</i>	03:41	Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	

Note. *BC*: curricular block, *DM*: duration in minutes, *FDE*: elaboration source, *ECP*: enriched with questions

<i>3rd ESO Descriptions of the videos worked with under the Flipped Learning model during the research</i>								
Objective	Content	BC	Video title	DM	Typology	FDE	ECP	Repository
Rhythm in music	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>El ritme y la pulsació</i>	04:49	Infographics animated using the web tool PowToon with	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom

				text and a music background				
Recognition of the period and culture of music in the Middle Ages	2. Listening 3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>Scriptorium</i>	02:56	Animated infographics with text and a music background	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Recognition of style, period, culture, and the most outstanding composers of musical Renaissance	2. Listening 3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>El Renacimiento musical</i>	05:50	Lesson-Presentation with text, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Characteristic instruments of Classicism and Romanticism: keyboard and notes. Height in the musical language: Anglo-Saxon alphabetical notation	2. Listening 3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>Teclat i Notes 1a part</i>	05:26	Lesson-Presentation with text, voice, and image of the teacher in some parts Lesson-Presentation with text, the teacher's voice, and a music background Lesson-Presentation with text, voice, and	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
		<i>2a part A</i>	03:36					
		<i>2ª part B</i>	04:43					

				image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background				
Opera	2. Listening 3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	What is opera?	02:37	Lesson-Presentation with text in English, the teacher's voice, and a music background	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Recognition of style, period, and culture of musical Classicism. Recognition of one of the most significant composers in musical Classicism	2. Listening 3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	Mozart	04:59	Lesson-Presentation with text, voice, and a music background	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	
Procedures for content presentation. Preparation of projects and presentations using ICTs for their production and dissemination	5. Transversal elements	Núvol de paraules 1ª part Núvol de paraules 2ª part	03:52 03:41	Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in	Elaborated by the authors Elaborated by the authors	Yes Yes	Edpuzzle Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot

				some parts, and a music background				
--	--	--	--	------------------------------------	--	--	--	--

Note. *BC*: curricular block, *DM*: duration in minutes, *FDE*: elaboration source, *ECP*: enriched with questions

<i>4th ESO Descriptions of the videos worked with under the Flipped Learning model during the research</i>								
Objective	Content	BC	Video title	DM	Typology	FDE	ECP	Repository
Elements of music: rhythm, harmony, melody, and timbre	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Elements de la música</i>	05:48	Lesson-Presentation and sound	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom
The musical form	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Form and Structure</i>	02:35	Lesson-Presentation with text and voice in English and the teacher's voice	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom
Capturing sound: earliest sound playing devices, earliest sound recordings, application of electricity, recording media/formats, new sound recording and playing devices, recording by tracks, analogic recording, digital recording	3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>Perseguint el so 1a part</i> <i>2ª part</i>	06:35	Lesson-Presentation with text, the teacher's voice, and image of the teacher at the beginning	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
			06:50			Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot

				Lesson-Presentation with text, the teacher's voice, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors			
Elements of a recording studio: the microphone	3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>Cómo funciona el micrófono</i>	05:04	Animated Lesson-Presentation with voice and a music background	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
Elements of a recording studio: music software. Audacity: open-access sound edition program	2. Listening 4. Music and technology	<i>Audacity guía usuari</i> <i>1a part</i> <i>2a part</i>	05:04	Lesson-Presentation with text and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom
			04:39	Lesson-Presentation with text and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom
Jazz: origins, worksong, gospelsong, blues, New Orleans style, ragtime, Dixieland style, Chicago style, piano stride style, swing, big bands	3. Musical and cultural contexts 4. Music and technology	<i>El Jazz 1ª part</i>	05:43	Infographics animated using the web tool PowToon with text, voice	YouTube	Yes	Edpuzzle	Traditional classroom

Autoría: Roig-Vila, Rosabel y Fabra-Brell, Eugenio

				and a music background				
Procedures for content presentation. Preparation of projects and presentations using ICTs for their production and dissemination	5. Transversal elements	<i>Núvol de paraules 1^a part</i>	03:52	Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	Gamified Kahoot
		<i>Núvol de paraules 2^a part</i>	03:41	Tutorial with text, the teacher's voice, image of the teacher in some parts, and a music background	Elaborated by the authors	Yes	Edpuzzle	

Note. *BC*: curricular block, *DM*: duration in minutes, *FDE*: elaboration source, *ECP*: enriched with questions